

AURAK
 الجامعة الأمريكية في رأس الخيمة
 AMERICAN UNIVERSITY OF RAS AL KHAIMAH

**DE MONTFORT
 UNIVERSITY
 DUBAI**

BLE 2024
 Program

The 1st International Conference on:

Business Management, Entrepreneurship, & Sustainable Circular Economy

04 - 05

NOV

2024

American University
 Of Ras Al Khaimah

Introduction:

IEREK – International Experts for Research Enrichment and Knowledge Exchange – is an international institution pioneering knowledge advancement and enhancing research internationally by organizing and managing conferences in various fields of knowledge. IEREK believes that a hybrid conference format, which combines in-person and virtual participation, offers increased accessibility, flexibility, and inclusivity. Hybrid conferences also offer cost efficiency by reducing travel and accommodation needs and contribute to sustainability by lowering the event's carbon footprint.

As delegates and speakers of the 1st International Conference on Business Management, Entrepreneurship, and Sustainable Circular Economy, you will be able to:

1. Obtain an internationally accredited certification of participation, which could boost your future academic career opportunities.
2. Discuss your research paper with professors, stakeholders, and other authors.
3. Participate in cutting-edge research workshops organized during the conference.
4. Ensure that your paper gets the maximum exposure in front of a relevant audience, as we share samples of publications in our weekly newsletter and online platforms.
5. Get the chance to publish your paper with Springer in the [ASTI Book Series](#).

About the BLE 1ST Edition:

The International Conference on “Business Management, Entrepreneurship, and Sustainable Circular Economy” aims to explore and discuss the intersection of these three crucial areas. The scope of the conference covers a wide range of topics related to business management practices, entrepreneurship, and the implementation of sustainable circular economy principles. Participants will have the opportunity to start discussions on innovative strategies for effective business management, including organizational behavior, strategic planning, marketing, and financial management. Additionally, the conference will emphasize the role of entrepreneurship in driving sustainable circular economy practices, encouraging creativity, and promoting sustainable business models. Important conversations on resource efficiency, waste reduction, product lifecycle management, and the development of circular supply chains will be held.

The BLE Conference is a significant event that will take place from November 4th to November 5th, 2024 which will held on American university at Ras AL Khaima, United Arab Emirates. The conference is organized with the valuable support and active participation of Springer Nature, a leading academic publisher. The proceedings of the conference will be indexed in Scopus, a renowned abstract and citation database, further enhancing the visibility and impact of the research presented.

The purpose of the BLE Conference is to bring together experts, researchers, practitioners, and policymakers from various disciplines to explore and promote the integration of business management practices, entrepreneurship, and sustainable circular economy principles. The conference aims to encourage a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities in these areas and to make knowledge exchange and collaboration easier. The conference seeks to inspire and empower participants to develop and implement sustainable business models that contribute to a circular economy. The goal is to drive positive change, promote environmental control, and enhance economic and social well-being through the intersection of business management, entrepreneurship, and sustainable circular economy practices.

Keynote Speakers

Dr. Dima Jamali,
Vice President of Academic Affairs, Canadian University Dubai |
President of Global Compact Network Lebanon

Gary Smith,
Head of Incubation Centre
Amity University Dubai.

DAY 1: 04 November 2024 – Monday

Venue: American University of Ras Al Khaimah

Address: ([Click for Map Location](#))

Program Time Zone: Ras Al Khaimah - United Arab Emirates (GMT+4)

Hall Name (Abdulla bin Ali Al Sharhan School of Arts and Sciences Building (K), Ibn Khaldun Auditorium, Ground Floor.)

Online attendance Link: contact ble@ierek-scholar.org for access

Download Latest Zoom Version: [Click here!](#)

Online Platform Guide: [Click here!](#)

Program Time Zone: Ras Al Khaimah - United Arab Emirates (GMT+4)

9:30 – 10:30 | **Welcome all/ Registration & Morning coffee**
Registration and Morning Coffee

10:30 – 11:00 | **Opening Ceremony**
Greetings and Welcome notes.

10:30 / **Main Host (Abdulla bin Ali Al Sharhan School of Arts and Sciences Building (K), Ibn Khaldun Auditorium, Ground Floor)**

10:30 – 10:40 | **Dr. David A. Schmidt**, President, American University of Ras Al Khaimah- United Arab Emirates

10:40 – 10:50 | **Dr. Tahseen Anwer Arshi**, Associate Provost for Research Sustainability/ Director - The Center for Innovation and Entrepreneurship, American University of Ras Al Khaimah.

10:50 – 11:05 | **IEREK TEAM: Welcome and Introduction**

10:50 – 10:55 | Dr. Mourad Amer, President and CEO of IEREK & ASTI' Series Editor by Springer.

10:55 – 11:05 | IEREK Team (*IEREK Presentation*)

11:05 / **Plenary Session**
Introducing Keynotes

11:05 - 11:35 | **Keynote Speech / Dr. Dima Jamali**, Vice President of Academic Affairs, Canadian University Dubai | President of Global Compact Network Lebanon
Speech Title: "University Best Practices in Entrepreneurial Education"

11:35 – 11:45 | **Short Break**

Hall Name :Abdulla bin Ali Al Sharhan School of Arts and Sciences Building (K), Ibn Khaldun Auditorium, Ground Floor.
The Dual Lens: Exploring Authorial and Editorial Insights in Research

By: Dr. Bronwyn P Wood

Internationally Experienced Academic Lead, UAE University
Co-editor-in-chief of the Journal Gender, Work & Organization [Scopus Q1, IF 3.2] (Wiley-Black-well Publishing).

11:45 – 13:00

13:00 – 14:00	<i>Lunch Break (Abdulla bin Ali Al Sharhan School of Arts and Sciences Building (K), Al Mawardi Multi-Purpose Hall, Ground Floor)</i>
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14:00 / Parallel Sessions

*All authors must commit to the time allowed for each paper presentation (15 minutes)
 *A brief discussion (Q&A) is to be allowed after each session (15 minutes)

Session 1: Saqr Library Building (J), Avicenna Auditorium, Second Floor		Session 2: RAK Business School Building (H), Averroes (Ibn Rushd) Multi-Purpose Hall, Ground Floor		Session 3: Abdulla bin Ali Al Sharhan School of Arts and Sciences Building (K), Ibn Khaldun Auditorium, Ground Floor	
Topic: Sustainable Business, Economics, and Financial Management (Hybrid)		Topic: Sustainable Business Models and Practices (Hybrid)		Topic: Sustainable Growth and CSR Strategies: Tourism, SMEs, and Empowering Entrepreneurship (Hybrid)	
Session Chair Dr Abdelfatah Arman Department Chair - Department of Management / Assistant Professor of Human Resource Management / Academic Integrity Officer Session Discussant Dr. Pranav Kumar Assistant Professor of Management with a specialization in Marketing		Session Chair Dr Mohamed Mahdi Abaker Associate Professor - Management / Alumni Coordinator and Beta Gamma Sigma Chapter Liaison Session Discussant Dr. Mohamad Kharseh Associate Professor		Session Chair Dr. Fatima Beena Faculty & Head of Innovation Hub at De Montfort University Dubai Session Discussant Dr. Nadir Ali Associate Professor at De Montfort University, Dubai	
14:00 – 14:15	Breaking Down Kuwait's Inflation Rate (BLE-2024-10) Layal Mansour	14:00 – 14:15	How Does Firm-Level Innovation Enhance High-Performance Work Systems? Evidence From Multinational Telecoms In Jordan (BLE-2024-78) Firas Armosh	14:00 – 14:15	Leveraging AI Enabled Social Capital For Sustainable Tourism (BLE-2024-43) Venkoba Rao, Tahseen Anwer Arshi
14:15 – 14:30	Gender Differences In Transformational Leadership And Their Impact On Organizational Outcomes: Insights From The UAE And Pakistan (BLE-2024-52) (Online) Mohamed Osman Shereif Mahdi Abaker, Sohana Intasa Siddiqua, Aamir Kibria.	14:15 – 14:30	The Impact of Online Data Collection On Consumer Autonomy: A Study In The UAE (BLE-2024-47) Abdelfatah Arman, Osama Sohaib, Vazeerjan Begum, Tariq Bhatti	14:15 – 14:30	Integrating Large Language Models (LLMs) Into Entrepreneurial Ventures: Exploring the Potential Of AI-Driven Innovation In Start-Ups (BLE-2024-68) Tahseen Anwer Arshi, Shashank Shah, Swapnil Morande
14:30 – 14:45	The Impact Of Applied Audit On Fraudulent Practices In Business Entities; Czech Republic Accountants' Experience (BLE-2024-75) Marie Paseková, Roman Sklenár.	14:30 – 14:45	Application Of Game Theory In Marketing Strategy: How To Choose The Perfect Game Industry-Wise (BLE-2024-87) (Online) Tanvi Sinha	14:30 – 14:45	Balancing Growth and Sustainability: Economic and Environmental Impacts of Tourism on Coastal Communities in Oman (BLE-2024-73) Ammar Albalushi
14:45 – 15:00	Commercial Banks' Performance In Emerging Markets: New Evidence From The MENAP Region (BLE-2024-33) (Online) Anas Azzabi	14:45 – 15:00	Innovative Renewable Energy Technologies For Sustainable Development (BLE-2024-86) Irshad Ahmad, Shagufta, Marco Masabuda, Zainab Masoud Hussein	14:45 – 15:00	Bridging Gaps: How Higher Education and CSR Can Foster Women's Entrepreneurship in Oman (BLE-2024-74) Nabila Almacki, Ammar Al Balushi
15:00 – 15:15	Entrepreneurship Challenges: Case Of Developing Economies (BLE-2024-48) Nighat Ansari	15:00 – 15:15	The Impact of AI and Machine Learning on Enhancing Risk Management Strategies in the UAE's IT Industry (BLE-2024-66) Shailendra Baghel, Moshood Oladapo	15:00 – 15:15	The Moderating Effect Of Sustainable Strategy On ESG Disclosure And Firm Performance Evidence From China's Strategic Emerging Industries (BLE-2024-36) (Online) Shenglian Wang

15:15 – 15:30	<i>Afternoon Coffee Break</i>				
15:30 – 15:45	Exchange Rate Flexibilization and Macroeconomic Determinants: Evidence from MENA Region (BLE-2024-35) (Online) Nouhaila Moutaib	15:30 – 15:45	Investigating Management Competencies Among Business Administration Students of Selected Higher Educational Institution (Heis) In the National Capital Region (NCR) (BLE-2024-58) (Online) Ronald Catapang	15:30 – 15:45	A Contemporary Research Study of CSR Challenges Faced by Omani SMEs (BLE-2024-79) Veena Tewari
15:45 – 16:00	Rate Of Satisfaction of Creditors By Debtors During Debt Relief Period (BLE-2024-70) Roman Sklenar, Marie Pasekova	15:45 – 16:00	Do retail investors in the UAE take ESG factors into account when making decisions? (BLE-2024-85) Neev Baruah	15:45 – 16:00	Theory Building or Theory Testing: How Can Artificial Intelligence Benefit Entrepreneurship Research? (BLE-2024-40) Tahseen Anwer Arshi
16:00 – 16:15	The Gestalt of Corporate Reputation and its Impact on Wall Street Anna Karenina vs. The Great Gatsby (BLE-2024-18) Jonathan Matzinger, Andreas Hediger	16:00 – 16:15	Harnessing Emotional Intelligence for Sustainable Engineering Practices (BLE-2024-23) (Online) Fadi Sayegh	16:00 – 16:15	Understanding Attitudes Towards Using Sustainable Technology: A Multi-Group Analysis Among Employees of Entrepreneurial Firms. (BLE-2024-109) (Online) Bente Fatema
16:15 – 16:30	Discussion & Q&A	16:15 – 16:30	Sustainability Development and Financial Performance of Banks in the United Kingdom (BLE-2024-108) Jafar Jamal Irshoud	16:15 – 16:30	Discussion & Q&A
		16:30 – 16:45	Discussion & Q&A		
End of Day 1 In-person / Hybrid Sessions					

DAY 2: 05 November 2024 –Tuesday

Venue: American University of Ras Al Khaimah
 Venue: Abdulla bin Ali Al Sharhan School of Arts and Sciences Building (K), Ibn Khaldun Auditorium, Ground Floor.
 Address: ([Click for Map Location](#))
 Program Time Zone: Ras Al Khaimah - United Arab Emirates (GMT+4)

Online attendance Link: contact ble@ierek-scholar.org for access
 Download Latest Zoom Version: [Click here!](#)
 Online Platform Guide: [Click here!](#)
 Program Time Zone: Ras Al Khaimah - United Arab Emirates (GMT+4)

10:00 – 11:00 | Welcome all/ registration & Morning coffee

Registration and Morning Coffee

11:00 – 11:30 | Keynote Speech 2| **Gary Smith**, BA (Hons), PGCE, MCIM, DipM, MSc. Head of Incubation Centre | Amity University Dubai.

Speech Title: “Entrepreneurship, EdTech, and AI Creating Skills of the Future.”

11:30 - 11:45 | **Moving to the Sessions**

11:45 / Parallel Sessions

*All authors must commit to the time allowed for each paper presentation (15 minutes)

*A brief discussion (Q&A) is to be allowed after each session (15 minutes)

Session 4: Abdulla bin Ali Al Sharhan School of Arts and Sciences Building (K), Ibn Khaldun Auditorium, Ground Floor		Session 5: Saqr Library Building (J), Avicenna Auditorium, Second Floor		Session 6: RAK Business School Building (H), Averroes (Ibn Rushd) Multi-Purpose Hall, Ground Floor	
Topic: Environmental Responsibility in Business (Hybrid)		Topic: Leadership Development for Globalization and Emerging Markets (Hybrid)		Topic: Social Responsibility and Community Engagement in Business (Hybrid)	
<p>Session Chair Prof. Irshad Ahmad Professor</p> <p>Session Discussant Dr. Shagufta Waseem Associate Professor</p>		<p>Session Chair Dr. Vazeerjan Begum Associate Dean / Associate Professor – Business Administration</p> <p>Session Discussant Dr. Khalid Khan Assistant Professor of Human Resource Management</p>		<p>Session Chair Dr. Roz-Ud-Din Nassar Professor</p> <p>Session Discussant Dr. Fathia Elmenghawi Assistant Professor</p>	
11:45 – 12:00	Circular Economy and Sustainable Materials in Campus Construction: Case Study of Campus Developments at American University of Ras Al Khaimah (BLE-2024-60) Fathia Elmenghawi	11:45 – 12:00	Leadership, Vision, and Progress: The Transformational Journey of Sheikh Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum in Shaping Dubai's Future (BLE-2024-83) Pranav Kumar	11:45 – 12:00	Navigating the Undercurrents: Risks and Resilience in Zambia's Hydropower-Dominated Energy Landscape (BLE-2024-12) (Online) Katlego Majola
12:00 – 12:15	Sustainable Development and Competitiveness of Coastal Tourism Destinations in Calabarzon Region, Philippines (BLE-2024-80) (Online) NoelahMae Borbon, Phoebe Dian D. Bansil	12:00 – 12:15	Transformational Leadership and Organizational Responsibility: New perspective (BLE-2024-17) (Online) Manal Elsayed, Yara Elsehaimy	12:00 – 12:15	What the Y2K Revival Means for the Sustainability of the High-End Fashion Sector (BLE-2024-64) Jie Sun

12:15 – 12:30	MLD/ZLD Based Sustainable Circular Management/Valorization of Desalination Brine for Resource Recovery (BLE-2024-114) Tirumala Uday Kumar Nutakki	12:15 – 12:30	Building Competitive Advantage through Sustainable Business Model: Strategic Analysis of Nirvana Retreat Farm (RAK) (BLE-2024-59) (Online) Iva Bulatovic	12:15 – 12:30	Leveraging Emiratization for Green Careers: A Pathway to Achieving UAE's Sustainability Goals (BLE-2024-46) Abdefatah Arman, Khalid Khan, Fady ElBorno
12:30 – 12:45	Corporate Governance and ESG Controversies: A Quantile Regression Approach (BLE-2024-84) Hailesalsie Gebremariam, Hussain Muhammad.	12:30 – 12:45	Leadership Behavior, Personality Factors, Intercultural Considerations, and Innovation a Cross-Cultural Research Perspective (BLE-2024-16) Robert Rossberger	12:30 – 12:45	The Future of Southern Africa: How ESG Can Shape a Sustainable and Resilient Region (BLE-2024-11) (Online) Katlego Majola
12:45 – 13:00	Benefits and challenges of implementing circular economy strategies beyond recycling in the plastics industry (BLE-2024-98)(Online) Myriam Ertz, Mehrdad KORDI	12:45 – 13:00	The Impact of Cultural Intelligence on Strategic Project Management (BLE-2024-69) (Online) Sami I.Mohtar	12:45 – 13:00	The Impact of cultural intelligence on global leaders' effectiveness: A comparative study of leaders in academic and professional organisations in the United Arab Emirate (BLE-2024-63) Moshood Oladapo, Ruchi Aggarwal, Sana Arshad, Nadia Imbasaat
13:00 – 13:15	Assessment of the Initial and Life-Cycle Costs, Energy, and Environmental Benefits of Concrete Produced with Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (BLE-2024-50) Rozuddin Nassar, Osama Sohaib	13:00 – 13:15	Training intervention based on Acceptance and Commitment Therapy for the improvement of psychological flexibility and professional wellbeing in leaders (BLE-2024-05) (Online) Marta Pérez Pérez	13:00 – 13:15	The Motivation of Generation Z to Embrace Sustainable Fashion Practices, Such as Purchasing Second-Hand Items (BLE-2024-65) Sawsan Mohammad Mostafa Elsharkawi, Jie Sun
13:15 – 14:15	Lunch Break (Abdulla bin Ali Al Sharhan School of Arts and Sciences Building (K), Al Mawardi Multi-Purpose Hall, Ground Floor)				
14:15 – 14:30	A systematic literature review of parcel delivery process from value creation lens: A research agenda (BLE-2024-113) Wafa Almazrouei	14:15 – 14:30	Sustainable Award Criteria and Firm Growth: Evidence from Spanish Public Auctions (BLE-2024-15) Davide Vannoni	14:15 – 14:30	Financing Aspects of Social Enterprises: Systematic Review Of The Literature And Thematic Mapping (BLE-2024-37) Dharmendra Singh, Raihan Taqui Syed
14:30 – 14:45	Circular Economy and Family Firms: Research Directions (BLE-2024-08) (Online) Marta Pérez Pérez	14:30 – 14:45	The Effective and Responsible Leadership in Hotel Management and its Influence to the Organizational Culture Awareness (BLE-2024-77) (Online) NoelahMae Borbon, Leslie Salazar	14:30 – 14:45	The Power of Women: Board Gender Diversity and Workplace Safety (BLE-2024-97) Zhao Xuwu
14:45 – 15:00	A Machine Learning Approach To Forecasting Energy Market Performance (BLE-2024-72) Mohamad Kharseh	14:45 – 15:00	Corporate governance mechanisms, board gender diversity, and strategic change (BLE-2024-49) Hussain Muhammad	14:45 – 15:00	Enhancing E-Commerce Recommendation Systems With Sentiment Analysis (BLE-2024-45) Osama Sohaib
15:00 – 15:15	Risk Assessment in Oman Construction Industry: A Quantitative Study of Uncertainty and Risk Attitudes in Project Management (BLE-2024-39) (Online) Omar Adwan	15:00 – 15:15	Sustainable Financial Management (SFM) in E-Banking: Strategies and Challenges in Dubai (BLE-2024-56) Rahul Jain	15:00 – 15:15	Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Environmental Sustainability in Education (BLE-2024-53) Minahil Kamran
15:15 – 15:30	Discussion & Q&A	15:15 – 15:30	Discussion & Q&A	15:15 – 15:30	Discussion & Q&A
End of Day 2 In-person / Hybrid Sessions					

15:30 – 15:45 | **Afternoon Coffee (Abdulla bin Ali Al Sharhan School of Arts and Sciences Building (K), Al Mawardi Multi-Purpose Hall, Ground Floor)**

15:45 – 16:00 | *Closing Ceremony*

Hall: *Abdulla bin Ali Al Sharhan School of Arts and Sciences Building (K), Al Mawardi Multi-Purpose Hall, Ground Floor*

15:45 – 15:55

Dr. Tahseen Anwer Arshi, Associate Provost for Research and Community Service / Director - The Center for Innovation and Entrepreneurship, American University of Ras Al Khaimah.

15:55 – 16:00

Group Photo

Closing Remarks